

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Design, synthesis, *in vitro* and *in vivo* characterization of selective NKCC1 inhibitors for the treatment of core symptoms in Down syndrome and other brain disorders.

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1. Aqueous kinetic solubility.

30 μL aliquots of 10 mM DMSO stock solution of the test compound were incubated in Phosphate Buffered Saline (PBS) at pH 7.4 at 25°C for 24h. After centrifugation the dissolved compound in the supernatant was quantified by LC-MS/MS. Target concentration was 250 μM resulting in a final concentration of 2.5% DMSO. Aqueous kinetic solubility was determined by UV quantification at 215 nm. Kinetic solubility was then calculated by dividing the peak area of the supernatant by the peak area of the reference and multiply by the reference concentration (μM) and dilution factor (1.25).

2. *In vitro* mouse plasma stability.

Compounds were diluted in preheated (37 °C) mouse plasma (Rockland Immunochemicals Inc.) with 5% DMSO to favor solubilization. The final compound concentration was 2.0 μM . At time points (0, 5, 15, 30, 60, 120 min), a 30 μL aliquot of the incubation solution was diluted in 200 μL of cold acetonitrile spiked with 200 nM Warfarin, as internal standard. After vortexing for 30 s, the solution was centrifuged at 3500g for 15 min at 4 °C, and the supernatant transferred for LC-MS/MS analysis on a Waters Acquity UPLC/MS TQD system. Compound stability was evaluated on the basis of the corresponding peak areas plotted *vs* time. The compounds' half-lives were calculated using a one-phase fitting decay of the peak area *vs* time profiles.

3. *In vitro* mouse microsomal stability.

10mM DMSO stock solution of test compound was pre-incubated at 37 °C for 15 min with liver microsomes (Sekisui Xenotech, LCC), 0.1M Tris-HCl buffer (pH 7.4), and 10% DMSO. The final concentration was 4.6 μM . After pre-incubation, the cofactors (NADPH, G6P, G6PDH, MgCl_2 pre-dissolved in 0.1M Tris-HCl) were added to the incubation mixture and the incubation was continued at 37 °C for 1h. At each time point (0, 5, 15, 30, 60 min), 30 μL of incubation mixture was diluted with 200 μL cold acetonitrile spiked with 200 nM of warfarin as internal standard, followed by centrifugation at 3500 g for 30 min. The supernatant was further diluted with H₂O (1:1) for analysis.

An aliquot of 200 μ l of the supernatant was removed, and the concentration of the test compound was quantified by LC-MS/MS. The percentage of the test compound remaining at each time point relative to $t=0$ was calculated. The half-lives ($t_{1/2}$) were determined by a one-phase decay equation using a non-linear regression of compound concentration vs time.

4. Figure S-1

Figure S-1. Pharmacophore fitting of unselective bumetanide derivatives. A-D) Overlap of bumetanide, benzmetanide, piretanide and furosemide (white sticks) onto the pharmacophore model (transparent spheres). Red arrows indicate features' mismatch, while in the middle circle is highlighted the pharmacophore hypothesis. Furosemide has the higher IC_{50} toward NKCC1 within the series of derivatives and shows a different fit into the model, lacking both the HB-acceptor in position 4 and the hydrophobic group in position 7.

5. Figure S-2

Figure S-2. Dose-response curve of 40 in young neurons with calcium influx assay.

6. Table S-1

compound	phase score		
27	1.62	4	1.50
7	1.56	22	1.50
5	1.56	20	1.50
11	1.56	25	1.49
15	1.56	3	1.49
23	1.56	42	1.49
9	1.54	40	1.49
30	1.54	37	1.47
19	1.54	1	1.47
16	1.53	21	1.46
10	1.52	28	1.46
6	1.51	43	1.46
17	1.51	32	1.45
31	1.51	34	1.45
8	1.51	33	1.44
18	1.51	41	1.44
13	1.51	44	1.44
12	1.51	36	1.42
14	1.51	38	1.41
29	1.51	39	1.13
26	1.51	35	1.07
24	1.50		

Table S-1. Ranking of NKCC1 inhibitors according to the phase score.

7. Table S-2.

% Object preference NOR

Objects	WT Vehicle	WT 40	Ts65Dn Vehicle	Ts65Dn 40	F and P (among groups)
A	27.58 ± 1.73	32.81 ± 2.60	30.95 ± 2.49	28.41 ± 2.91	Two-way ANOVA $F_{interaction(1,46)} = 2.590, P=0.114$
B	39.48 ± 2.19	34.35 ± 3.00	31.72 ± 1.83	38.58 ± 2.14	Two-way ANOVA $F_{interaction(1,46)} = 6.699, P=0.013$ Tukey <i>post hoc</i> test Within Vehicle WT vs Ts $P=0.018$ Within Ts Vehicle vs 40 $P=0.045$
C	32.94 ± 1.68	32.84 ± 2.67	37.33 ± 3.21	33.01 ± 2.06	Two-way ANOVA $F_{interaction(1,46)} = 0.764, P=0.387$
F and P (among objects)	One Way ANOVA $F_{interaction(2,42)} = 10.047, P<0.001$ B vs A $P<0.001$ B vs C $P=0.047$	One Way ANOVA $F_{interaction(2,30)} = 0.101, P=0.904$	One Way ANOVA $F_{interaction(2,33)} = 1.831, P=0.176$	One Way ANOVA $F_{interaction(2,33)} = 4.496, P=0.019$ B vs A $P=0.014$	

Total Exploration Time (sec) NOR

	WT Vehicle	WT 40	Ts65Dn Vehicle	Ts65Dn 40	F and P
Acquisition	107.30 ± 7.46	104.90 ± 7.89	85.96 ± 7.94	120.20 ± 14.5	Two-way ANOVA $F_{interaction(1,46)} = 3.477, P=0.069$
Trial	74.85 ± 5.79	76.64 ± 10.17	68.54 ± 5.67	76.14 ± 7.30	Two-way ANOVA $F_{interaction(1,46)} = 0.161, P=0.690$

Freezing Time (%) CFC

	WT Vehicle	WT 40	Ts65Dn Vehicle	Ts65Dn 40	F and P
Pre Shock	3.38 ± 0.42	2.34 ± 0.34	2.98 ± 0.65	2.75 ± 0.38	Two-way ANOVA $F_{interaction(1,44)} = 0.736, P=0.396$
Post Shock	53.75 ± 5.33	53.44 ± 6.88	59.28 ± 2.99	62.18 ± 4.18	Two-way ANOVA on Ranks $F_{interaction(1,44)} = 0.0693, P=0.794$
New Context	5.35 ± 0.96	3.33 ± 1.20	8.65 ± 1.10	7.34 ± 1.32	Two-way ANOVA $F_{genotype(1,44)} = 10.143, P=0.003$ Within Vehicle WT vs Ts $P=0.044$ Within 40 WT vs Ts $P=0.019$

Table S-2. Control parameters in the NOR and CFC tasks of WT and Ts65Dn mice.

8. ^1H , ^{13}C and ^{19}F Spectra of final compounds.

NMR experiments were run on a Bruker AVANCE III 400 system (400.13 MHz for ^1H and 100.62 MHz for ^{13}C), equipped with a BBI probe and Z-gradients, and Bruker FT NMR AVANCE III 600 MHz spectrometer equipped with a 5mmCryoProbe QCI $^1\text{H}/^{19}\text{F}-^{13}\text{C}/^{15}\text{N}-\text{D}$ quadruple resonance, a shielded Z-gradient coil and the automatic sample changer SampleJet NMR system (600 MHz for ^1H , 151 MHz for ^{13}C , and 565 MHz for ^{19}F). Spectra were acquired at 300 K, using deuterated dimethylsulfoxide ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$) or deuterated chloroform (CDCl_3) as solvents.

9. Chromatographic analysis of key compounds.

Performed on a Waters ACQUITY UPLC/MS system consisting of a SQD (Single Quadrupole Detector) Mass Spectrometer equipped with an Electrospray Ionization interface and a Photodiode Array Detector. The PDA range was 210-400nm. Analyses were performed on an ACQUITY UPLC BEH C₁₈ column (100x2.1mmID, particle size 1.7µm) with a VanGuard BEH C₁₈ pre-column (5x2.1mmID, particle size 1.7µm). Mobile phase was 10mM NH₄OAc in H₂O at pH 5 adjusted with AcOH (A) and 10mM NH₄OAc in MeCN-H₂O (95:5) at pH 5 (B). Linear Gradient: start at 10% B, hold for 0.20min, then 10-90%B in 6min, 90-100%B in 0.10min and 100% B hold for 0.70min. Total run time: 7min. Electrospray ionization in positive and negative mode. All final compounds displayed ≥ 95% purity by UPLC/MS analysis with the exception of compounds **15** (92%) and **16** (90%).

Compound 1

Compound 3

Compound 4

Compound 5

Compound 6

Compound 7

Compound 8

Compound 9

Compound 10

Compound 11

Compound 12

Compound 13

Compound 14

Compound 15

Compound 16

Compound 17

Compound 18

Compound 19

Compound 20

Compound 21

Compound 22

Compound 23

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Compound 25

Compound 26

Compound 27

Compound 28

Compound 29

Compound 30

Compound 31

Compound 32

Compound 33

Compound 34

Compound 35

Compound 36

Compound 37

Compound 38

Compound 39

Compound 40

Compound 41

Compound 42

Compound 43

